

JRP MultiFixRad

Guide for filling high temperature fixed points

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Introduction

This guide presents the basic techniques for filling metal-carbon cells at LNE-Cnam using the piston method. It deals with filling methods of eutectic cells (Fe-C, Co-C ...) and cells made of pure metals (Al, Ag ...). This document consists in five parts:

1. Identification and assembly of the graphite parts
2. Preparation of the eutectic mixture or pure metal
3. Inserting the metal into the cell
4. Melting and freezing cycles
5. Separation of the extension and cell finishing

1. Identification and assembly of the graphite parts

A set to construct a cell is composed of 9 different parts identified as follows and a high purity flexible graphite foil (or C/C sheet).

The assembly should be handled with care on a clean surface wearing gloves. All parts can be assembled with no modification except the crucible (if needed) and the stick. The crucible opening, with a diameter of 3 mm, can be enlarged by up to 5 mm to fit the pyrometer field spot. If possible, the opening should be at least two or three times larger than the field stop. If the modification is required, it should be done with precaution before the assembly using a well sharpened drill bit pre-cleaned with alcohol.

The assembly is as follows: The cavity is first inserted in the crucible, then the graphite foils (or C/C sheet) are wrapped inside the crucible. The gap between the crucible and the sleeve (mounted in the next step) is 1.3 mm. It was designed to allow the insertion of two layers of C/C sheet with a thickness of around 0.65 mm. In case the C/C sheets are replaced by a thinner graphite foil, only one foil,

wrapped around the sleeve can replace the two layers. Once the C/C sheets or the graphite foil(s) are in place, the sleeve is inserted. Its upper part should be at the same level, or possibly, only 0.1 or 0.2 mm above the top of the crucible (figure 1). If not, this means there is some gap between the cavity and the sleeve which should therefore be removed and re-inserted correctly.

Figure 1: the upper part of the crucible and the sleeve must be at the same level.

The extension is then screwed on the crucible which is ready to be filled.

2. Preparation of the eutectic mixture or pure metal

The tools and the containers used to mix the carbon and the metal must be pre-cleaned with alcohol. There is no need to prepare the metal-carbon mixture under argon atmosphere, a clean environment is enough. The proportion of graphite should be less than the eutectic composition as the sleeve (and the cavity to a lesser extent) contributes to the supply of graphite to the ingot. Table 1 gives the recommended proportions of C, in percentage of mass, to be mixed with the metal. These proportions can be adjusted within +/- 30 %.

Table 1: recommended proportion of carbon to be mixed with metal.

Alloy	Phase transition °C	Density of pure metal (at 20°C) g/cm ³	Eutectic proportion of C % mass C	Recommended proportion of C % mass	Tolerance	Density eutectic / density pure metal
Fe-C	1153	7.9	4.3	3.5	30 %	90 %
Co-C	1324	8.9	2.6	2		
Pd-C	1492	12.0	4.0	3		
Pt-C	1738	21,4	1.2	0.5		
Re-C	2474	20.8	1.3	0.5		

Quantity to be prepared for eutectic fixed points:

The volume of the crucible is expected to be completely filled by the molten mixture. This means, due to the thermal expansion of the ingot, that the volume of the ingot is less than that of the crucible at room temperature. Additionally, the density of the eutectic mixture is less than that of pure metal. These two comments together show that the estimated density of the eutectic mixture (mass of the mixture divided by the initial volume of the crucible) is only about 90 % of that of the pure metal. As an example, assuming a crucible volume of 3.49 cm³, the mass of pure Re to be prepared for a Re-C cell

is $20.8 \text{ g/cm}^3 \times 3.49 \text{ cm}^3 \times 90 \% = 65 \text{ g}$, rounded to 70 g because of the possible increase of the sleeve inner volume which has contributed to supply graphite to the mixture.

Quantity to be prepared for pure metal fixed points:

The thermal expansion of metal used for pure metal fixed points is generally 1.5 to 3 times larger than that of metals of eutectic fixed points. This means that an ingot made of pure metal shrinks more than a eutectic ingot at room temperature. However, the inner surface of the sleeve remains intact as there is no segregation of graphite during the melt. The quantity can therefore be estimated in the same way. As an example, assuming a crucible volume of 3.49 cm^3 , the mass of pure Ag to be prepared for a Ag cell is $10.5 \text{ g/cm}^3 \times 3.49 \text{ cm}^3 \times 90 \% = 33 \text{ g}$ rounded to 38 g for the first cell and adjusted more precisely for the next ones. It should be noted that, even for pure metals, the ingot mass vary sometimes by more than 5 %.

3. Inserting the metal into the cell

After preparation, the mixture (or pure metal) is poured inside the extension (on which is screwed the crucible shown in figure 1). The totality of the mixture may be introduced at once, but in most cases, it is better to fill a cell in 2 or 3 separated fillings. The number of fillings depends mainly on the initial shape of the metal. Four cases are possibles:

1. Case 1: Pure metal in cubes or shots (ex: Al or Ag)

All the metal can be poured into the crucible at once. Once the crucible is filled, the ring is put in the extension, the conical side in contact with the metal. The piston is then inserted in the extension to measure its stroke, which is generally between 15 and 30 mm.

2. Case 2: Pure metal in cubes or shots mixed with graphite powder (ex: Fe-C or Co-C)

The cell can be filled in only one step as in the case 1 described above. However, it is recommended to fill in two steps (or even three), to be able to observe the surface of the ingot after the first filling, and to make it more homogeneous. For the first step, it is recommended that the metal be poured in such a way that it is completely contained in the cell, without any contact with the extension, which will then be removed easily, to observe the ingot at the completion of the first melt.

3. Case 3: Pure metal in powder (ex: Al or Ag)

The low density of metal powder does not allow the filling in one step, so 2 steps are required. But unlike case 2, there is no reaction between the molten metal and the graphite, so the powder can be in contact with the extension (on 2 or 3 cm), even for the first filling. The metal can be compacted with the piston.

4. Case 4: Pure metal in powder mixed with graphite powder (ex: Fe-C or Co-C)

As case 3, the low density of metal powder does not allow the filling in one step. A minimum of 2 steps is required, but by precaution, it is better to fill the first cells in 3 or 4 steps, at least for the first attempts.

Unlike pure metals (Al, Ag ...), the metal-carbon mixture generally migrates into the graphite solid parts and deteriorates the surface. To preserve the extension and make it easier to remove it at the end, it is recommended for the 2 first fillings to avoid any contact between the mixture and the extension.

This means that the mixture is entirely contained in the sleeve. The mixture can be compacted using the piston which gives at the same time the quantity not to exceed.

4. Melting and freezing cycles

Before installing the cell, the furnace is first cycled (vacuum / argon) at room temperature to remove the oxygen. The cell is then placed in a cell holder or on a support, with the help of a tool, held with the clearance at the top of the extension. The crucible should be positioned in the flattest temperature gradient, having noticed it may shift due to the furnace vertical position or to the conduction along the stick (when in place).

In case the filling requires further steps (cases 2, 3, 4, §3), the first ones are performed with the stopper placed at the top of the extension to protect the metal from impurities. It is replaced at the last filling by the ring, the piston and the stick. In case one, the stopper is not used while ring, piston, and stick are used for the first and unique step.

The furnace is then heated up at a temperature which should not exceed $t_{melt} + 50$ °C, to limit the segregation of graphite from the graphite walls to the mixture. The corresponding setpoint should therefore be known in advanced. The heating slope should not be higher than 2500 °C/h. When the metal starts melting, the setpoint is left at $t_{melt} + 50$ °C for 15 minutes and then slow down to $t_{melt} - 30$ °C for about 10 minutes. The cooling slope is then applied up to room temperature. It should not be higher than - 1500 °C/h to avoid any thermal shock. Note that, even with the movable cavity, the breakage is still possible. The main risk is when the cell is removed from the furnace while it is still at 200 °C or 300 °C. For this reason, it is advised to remove the cell when the furnace temperature is below 50 °C.

Once the cell is at room temperature, the extension is removed from the crucible to inspect the metal which should be spread around the cavity. Because of the surface tension of the molten metal (especially at peritectic points, but also at the Fe-C and the Co-C points) an asymmetry in the ingot is sometimes seen but is not a problem at this stage.

A segregation of graphite powder can be seen at the surface of the ingot. This means that the proportion of C or that the temperature setpoint of the furnace was too high. In this case, the excess of graphite at the surface of the ingot should be removed before the next filling.

Only the last filling (the only one in case 1) requires the use of the ring and the piston. When at this stage, the rest of the mixture (the totality in case 1) is poured inside the extension and the ring is inserted, its conical side being in contact with the metal. The cell (with the extension) is then put inside the furnace, followed by the piston screwed on the stick. Note that the stick should be previously modified following the drawing figure 2.

Figure 2: Before using the stick, the thread should be slightly sawn to allow air to escape from the extension when the piston is pushed.

Once the installation is done, it is important to check that the stick can move freely along its axis, as the axis of the extension may not be perfectly aligned to that of the piston. The cell can then be heated respecting heating and freezing slopes of less than 2500 °C/h and 1500 °C/h respectively.

At the beginning of the melt, the piston sometimes drops automatically. This is often the case with pure metals (Al, Ag...). In the case of eutectics, the molten mixture generally migrates in the gap between the extension and the ring, blocking the latter as the excess of graphite around the gap causes the mixture to freeze. The ring can be unlocked by lightly knocking the stick (...). Once the metal (or the mixture) is entirely melted, the stick is pushed until it is in contact with the extension. In case of a doubt, do not pump on the piston. Apply the cooling slope and remove the cell from the furnace to see if the piston is at the end of its stroke. Note that the cell holder can move when the furnace is heated up and may cause the stick to move, leading a doubt on its position. The piston stroke should therefore be checked, not only at room temperature, but also just before the melt.

5. Separation of the extension and cell finishing

Once the cell is at room temperature, the excess of metal can be seen inside the piston. The extension can sometimes be unscrewed by turning it quite firmly to twist the metal on itself inside the piston. The sample is sometimes automatically separated from the ingot because of the shrink of the metal when the temperature drops. This is often the case with pure metals.

The most often, the part "01 Crucible" and the C/C sheets (or foils) can be separated from the extension, while the rest of the parts (ingot, cavity, sleeve, ring, extension and piston) are stuck together. In this case, the extension and the piston might be separated from the useful part (ingot, sleeve, cavity and ring) by twisting the two main parts.

When the extension cannot be separated from the cell, it should be carefully cut, 2 or 3 mm above the flat surface of the ring. The rest of the piston and the extension can then be broken using adapted tools.